

Green Rheology Modifiers: Enhancing Dye Printing Efficiency using Acrylated Flaxseed-Based Thickeners

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Abstract:

Thickeners control pastes rheology, dye transfer, and fixing efficiency, making them essential in textile printing. The stability, color compatibility, and reproducibility of conventional natural and modified polysaccharide thickeners are limited, while synthetic versions pose toxicological and environmental issues. In order to improve performance in Direct, Reactive, and Disperse dye printing, this study examines flaxseed gel as an environmentally acceptable thickener and assesses derivatives modified by acrylation. The findings show that acrylated modified thickeners provide better color strength and washing fastness than gum indalca, ZnO and TiO₂ modified thickeners. Notably, a 40.27% increase in color strength is achieved in Reactive dye printing, with consistently high performance observed across all dye classes. These findings highlight the strong potential of acrylated flaxseed-based thickeners as sustainable, high-efficiency rheology modifiers, contributing to advancements in green and performance-driven textile printing technology.

Keywords: Color strength, Flaxseed, Printing, Sustainable, Thickeners

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1. Introduction

A thickener is a substance that can increase the viscosity of a liquid without significantly altering its other properties. Commonly used in the food industry, thickeners help to thicken sauces, soups, and puddings without changing their taste. They are also used in textiles, paints, inks, explosives, and cosmetics. Thickening agents can be classified into two categories: polysaccharides and proteins. Thickeners may also improve the suspension of other ingredients or emulsions, thereby increasing the stability of the product. Some thickening agents are also gelling agents (gellants), which form a gel by dissolving in the liquid phase as a colloid mixture, creating a weakly cohesive internal structure [1-3].

Thickeners play a crucial role in textile printing by providing the appropriate viscosity to the print paste, holding dye particles in place to prevent spreading, and extracting sufficient condensed water during steaming to ensure dye transfer and fixation onto the fabric. Essential requirements for thickeners include good stability, specific physical and chemical properties such as viscosity and flow, and compatibility with other ingredients in the printing paste like oxidizing agents, acids, alkalis, and solvents. The thickener film must dry properly to avoid capillary spreading of color and allow effective water extraction during steaming, ensuring dye movement towards the fabric. Thickeners should not have an affinity for the dye, must control free water pick-up to prevent dye bleeding, and should be easily removable during washing. Additionally, they should be cost-effective and readily available [4-5].

Natural thickeners [6], derived from cereals (e.g., maize, wheat, rice), plant exudates (e.g., gum tragacanth, gum arabic, gum karaya), roots and seeds (e.g., guar gum, locust bean gum), and seaweeds (e.g., sodium alginate), offer the advantages of being cheap, easily available, and providing good viscosity at low concentrations. They are also suitable for printing with direct dyes. However, they have limitations, such as poor keeping properties, a harsh feel due to higher solid content, unsuitability for reactive dyes (except sodium alginate), and pigment printing. Natural modified thickeners, such as starch derivatives (e.g., British gum, carboxymethyl starch), gum derivatives (e.g., Meypro gum, gum indalca), and cellulose derivatives (e.g., CMC, HEC), improve keeping properties through modifications like etherification and esterification, making them suitable for most dyes except reactive ones [7-9]. Despite their benefits, they are costlier, have limited availability due to food regulations, and face production uncertainties from natural disasters [10]. Synthetic thickeners, such as acrylic (e.g., polyacrylic acid) and vinyl (e.g., polyvinyl alcohol), provide good viscosity at low concentrations without harshness, making them suitable for pigment printing and disperse dyes. Their main drawbacks are sensitivity to electrolytes and limited compatibility with other ingredients. Emulsion thickeners, including oil in water and water in oil types, are ideal for pigment printing due to minimal solid content and a soft fabric feel. They eliminate the need for washing, as oil and water evaporate during polymerization, fixing the prints. However, they are costly, pose fire hazards, and emit harmful vapors, posing health risks to workers [11].

In this study, an attempt has been made to explore the possibility of flaxseed gel [12] as a thickener in printing

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offers a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to synthetic thickeners, which are known to have negative environmental impacts, cause skin irritations, allergies, and are generally toxic and non-biocompatible. Flaxseed gel, a water-based thickener, shares similarities with cellulose derivatives and other natural thickeners, making it compatible with various dyes while being environmentally friendly. Research highlights the significant influence of thickeners on print performance, affecting rheology, adhesion, viscosity, and keeping properties. The concentration of the thickener and its interaction with additives play a crucial role in these properties. Recent advancements in nanotechnology have introduced nanoscale thickeners, which enhance viscosity control, fastness properties, and keeping properties. The literature emphasizes the importance of thickeners in optimizing printing processes, ensuring consistency across different fabrics and dyes, and fostering innovation in printing technology. Flaxseed gel's advantages include biocompatibility, non-toxicity, environmental friendliness, safety for human skin, non-polluting nature, and sustainability, making it a promising alternative in the printing industry.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The 60X59 plain woven scoured and bleached fabric 100% cotton cambric fabric (164 g/m²) was used for study. Both warp and weft yarns were of 20s count.

For disperse dye printing the 73x66 plain woven scoured and bleached 100% polyester fabric (169 g/m²) was used for the study. Both warp and weft yarns were of 30 deniers.

The chemicals, namely sodium alginate, gum indalca, urea, trisodium phosphate, resist salt, sodium bicarbonate, sodium chlorate, and tartaric acid of LR grade, manufactured by Merck (I) Ltd., were used for the preparation of the printing paste. Reactive and disperse dyes used were Coractive Red P4B and Coralene Dark Red 2B from Colourtex, respectively, and the direct dye Direct Red 111 from Prima Chemicals, Gujarat.

2.2 Methods

Flaxseed Gel Extraction

To prepare the flaxseed gel at concentrations of 12%, 14%, 16%, 18%, and 20%, begin by weighing the whole flaxseeds and water according to the required concentration. Start boiling the mixture and continue boiling for 10-15 minutes until it turns into a gel-like solution. Use a nylon mesh to strain the mixture, separating the seeds from the gel. Allow the gel to cool before using it for further processing. Viscosity was checked on LABMAN digital viscometer model LMDV-200.

Modification of Extracted Gel and Metal oxide Addition
Incorporating acrylation into flaxseed gel offers several

enhancements, notably improved stability under varying conditions such as temperature, pH, and exposure to light and air. These modifications provide structural reinforcement and prevent degradation, ensuring the gel's integrity. Additionally, metal oxides impart new functionalities like UV protection, antimicrobial activity, and moisture retention. They also enhance the gel's texture and rheological properties, improving viscosity, elasticity, and spread ability, which enhances user experience and application methods. Furthermore, the antimicrobial properties of metal oxides and acrylation extend the shelf life of flaxseed gel by inhibiting microbial growth, making it more suitable for long-term storage.

The extraction of flaxseed gel begins by boiling flaxseeds in water, which releases mucilage that forms a gel-like substance. This gel is separated from the seeds through filtration or centrifugation. The preparation of an acrylation solution involves dissolving acrylic monomers, such as acrylic acid, in a solvent. These monomers, containing reactive double bonds (C=C), can undergo addition reactions with functional groups in the flaxseed gel. During the acrylation reaction, the flaxseed gel is mixed or immersed in the acrylation solution. Under appropriate conditions, such as elevated temperature and the presence of a catalyst or initiator like potassium persulfate, the acrylic monomer reacts with functional groups (e.g., hydroxyl groups) in the gel, resulting in the covalent attachment of acrylic groups to the polymer backbone. After the acrylation reaction, the acrylated flaxseed gel is purified to remove unreacted monomers, catalysts, and byproducts through methods like washing, filtration, or precipitation. The purified acrylated flaxseed gel is then isolated for further characterization and use.

Printing Trials

Printing was carried out on cotton using direct and reactive dyes, and on polyester fabric using disperse dye. This was done by using a conventional thickener (Gum Indalca/Sodium Alginate), unmodified flaxseed thickener, and modified flaxseed thickener. The printing recipe ingredients are shown in Table 1, Table 2, and Table 3 for direct dye, reactive dye, and disperse dye, respectively.

Table 1 - Direct dye print paste formulation

Ingredients	Quantity in parts			
	Conventional	Unmodified	Formulated	Modified
Direct Red 111	1	1	1	1
Urea	2	2	2	2
Trisodium Phosphate	3	3	3	3
Water	5	5	5	5
Gum Indalca	89	-	-	-
Flaxseed gel Thickener	-	89	85	-
TiO ₂	-	-	4	-
Flaxseed gel Thickener (Acrylated)	-	-	-	89
Total	100	100	100	100

All samples were printed with print paste under neutral conditions. Then, it was dried after printing at temperatures below 80°C. Next, the fabric was steamed at 102°C for 1 hour. After steaming, the fabric was treated with 3 g/L cationic dye fixing agent at room temperature for 20 minutes. This was followed by a cold wash, and finally, the fabric was dried.

Table 2 - Reactive dye print paste formulation

Ingredients	Quantity in Parts			
	Conventional	Unmodified	Formulated	Modified
Coractive Red P4B	1	1	1	1
Urea	2	2	2	2
Resist Salt	1	1	1	1
Sodium Bicarbonate	3	3	3	3
Water	5	5	5	5
Sodium Alginate	88	-	-	-
Flaxseed gel Thickener	-	88	84	-
TiO ₂	-	-	4	-
Flaxseed gel Thickener (Acrylated)	-	-	-	88
Total	100	100	100	100

All samples were printed with print paste under neutral conditions. After drying, the fabric was steamed at 105°C for 1 hour. After steaming, the fabric was washed with hot water, then treated with 2 g/L soap at boiling temperature for 20 minutes. This was followed by a hot wash and a cold wash. Finally, the fabric was dried.

Table 3 -Disperse dye print paste formulation

Ingredients	Quantity in Parts			
	Conventional	Unmodified	Formulated	Modified
Coralene Dark Red 2B	1	1	1	1
Sodium Chlorate	1	1	1	1
Tartaric Acid	1	1	1	1
Water	5	5	5	5
Sodium Alginate	92	-	-	-
Flaxseed gel Thickener	-	92	88	-
TiO ₂	-	-	4	-
Flaxseed gel Thickener (Acrylated)	-	-	-	92
Total	100	100	100	100

All samples were printed with print paste under neutral conditions. After drying, the fabric was steamed at 130°C for 20 minutes. After steaming, the fabric was washed with hot water, then treated with 2 g/L caustic and 2 g/L Sodium

dithionite at 60°C temperature for 20 minutes. This was followed by a hot wash and a cold wash. Finally, the fabric was dried.

2.3 Testing and Analysis

The viscosity of the extracted gel at different concentrations was checked, and the viscosity of modified acrylated thickeners was also checked using a LABMAN digital viscometer, model LMDV-200. The keeping property of unmodified and modified thickening agents is also checked by change in viscosity.

Washing fastness of cotton and polyester fabric printed by using modified and unmodified thickening agent was determined by IS 13036 (1991).

The color strength difference of cotton and polyester fabrics printed using modified and unmodified thickening agents was determined on X-Rite color matching system CI42 UV spectrophotometer, employing the CIE formula, with a D65 light source and a 10° observer.

3. Result and Discussion

A shown in Fig.1a line graph is plotted and viscosity is measure on digital viscometer (Fig.1b) to understand the viscosity behavior of flax-seed gel against its concentration. The study also examines whether the viscosity of the gel decreases after stirring compared to before stirring.

Figure 1 - a) Effect of concentration of flex seed on viscosity b) Digital viscometer

The viscosity increases as the concentration of flaxseed gel increases. It is observed that the viscosity drops to some extent after stirring the flaxseed gel. An 18% concentration of thickener is used for all trials, as it is deemed suitable for the printing paste.

Table 4 - Colour strength Direct, Reactive and Disperse printed samples by using various thickener

Thickener	Strength in %		
	Direct	Reactive	Disperse
Gum indalca	100	-	100
Sodium Alginate	-	100	-
Unmodified flaxseed	62.74	80.09	97.12
ZnO modified	70.87	89.50	155.66
TiO ₂ Modified	61.04	55.20	147.02
Acrylated Modified	140.76	140.27	249.92

Table 5 - Washing fastness rating of Direct, Reactive and Disperse printed samples by using various thickener

Thickener	Direct			Reactive			Disperse		
	1 st Adjacent Fabric	2 nd Adjacent Fabric	Colour Difference	1 st Adjacent Fabric	2 nd Adjacent Fabric	Colour Difference	1 st Adjacent Fabric	2 nd Adjacent Fabric	Colour Difference
Gum indalca	5	5	4-5	-	-	-	5	5	4-5
Sodium Alginate	-	-	-	5	5	4-5	-	-	-
Unmodified flaxseed	4	4	4-5	4	4	3-4	4	4	3-4
ZnO Modified	4	4	5	4	4	3	4	4	4-5
TiO2 Modified	4	4	5	4	4	4-5	4	4	3-4
Acrylation Modified	5	5	3-4	5	5	4	5	5	4

Experiments were conducted using 1% Direct dye, 1% Reactive dye, and 1% Disperse dye, following the procedures and recipes mentioned in Tables 1, 2, and 3. When comparing the results to the standard thickeners for direct dye, Gum Indalca and Sodium alginate, both set at 100% as shown in Table 4 and Fig.2-4, it was observed that the acrylation modification yielded superior results across all dye types. Specifically, acrylation showed a 40.76% increase in color strength for Direct dye, a 40.27% increase for Reactive dye, and a 49.22% increase for Disperse dye. This improvement is likely due to the acrylation process producing a homogeneous mixture, which enhances dye dissolution and provides more stability to the flaxseed gel. The ZnO/TiO2 modification also gave good results, with approximately a 50% increase in color strength for Disperse dye. However, the TiO2 modification resulted in significantly poorer performance for both Direct and Reactive dyes, with decreases in color strength of 38.96% and 44.8% respectively, likely due to the fine particle size of ZnO and TiO2 clogging the screen. Additionally, the unmodified flaxseed thickener performed 2.88% worse than the standard for Disperse dye and showed a 10% decrease in color strength for Reactive dye, likely because it does not form a homogeneous mixture, hindering its ability to pass through the screen properly. The other modifications fell between the results of the acrylation and TiO2 modifications.

As shown in Table 5, the color fastness to washing was evaluated by ISO 105 test method and experiments for direct dye, reactive dye, and disperse dye printed samples involved

using adjacent fabrics: Cotton and Wool for direct and reactive dyes, and Polyester and Cotton for disperse dye. Ratings were conducted using the grey scale, assessing color difference for the original samples and color staining for adjacent fabrics. For direct dyes, both Cotton and Wool adjacent fabrics exhibited excellent color staining ratings with Gum Indalca and acrylation modifications, attributed to enhanced viscosity and stability of the printing paste. The unmodified flaxseed, ZnO, and TiO2 modifications showed good color staining ratings. Additionally, the color difference of printed Cotton received excellent ratings for ZnO and TiO2 modifications, and good to excellent ratings for Gum Indalca and acrylation modifications, indicating improved paste homogeneity. For reactive dyes, Cotton and Wool fabrics similarly showed excellent color staining with sodium alginate and acrylation modifications, while unmodified flaxseed exhibited good ratings. The ZnO and TiO2 modifications also showed good performance. The color difference ratings for Cotton were good to excellent with sodium alginate and TiO2, and average to good with acrylation and unmodified flaxseed. In disperse dyes, Polyester and Cotton fabrics displayed excellent color staining ratings with Gum Indalca and acrylation modifications, and good ratings with unmodified flaxseed, ZnO, and TiO2 modifications. The color difference ratings for printed Disperse dye were good to excellent with Gum Indalca and ZnO modifications, good with acrylation, and average to good with unmodified flaxseed and TiO2 modifications.

Figure 2 - Printed Samples of Direct Red111

Sodium alginate Thickener Unmodified flaxseed thickener Modified with ZnO Modified with acrylation Modified with TiO2

Figure 3 - Printed Samples of Coractive Red P4B

Gum indalca thickener Unmodified flaxseed thickener Modified with ZnO Modified with TiO2 Modified with Acrylation

Figure 4 - Printed Samples of Coralene Dark Red 2B

4. Conclusions

Based on the findings from Direct, Reactive, and Disperse dye printing processes, acrylated modified thickeners consistently demonstrate superior performance in terms of color strength and color fastness to washing compared to their counterparts such as ZnO and TiO₂ modified thickeners, as well as gum indalca thickeners. Specifically,

acrylated modified thickeners show remarkable results with a 140.27% increase in color strength in Reactive dye printing and excellent performance across all dye types. These findings underscore the potential of acrylation-modified thickeners as a versatile and sustainable choice for enhancing dyeing processes, promising significant advancements in textile printing technology.

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